

ROLE OF AYURVEDA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF DIABETIC FOOT ULCER- CLINICAL EVIDENCE A CASE STUDY

*¹Dr. Prathiksha V., ²Dr. Duragappa Harijan

¹Post Graduate Scholar.

²Professor.

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Prathiksha V.

Post Graduate Scholar.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18439494>

How to cite this Article: *¹Dr. Prathiksha V., ²Dr. Duragappa Harijan. (2026). Role of Ayurveda In The Management of Diabetic Foot Ulcer- Clinical Evidence A Case Study. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 12(2), 71–75. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 29/12/2025

Article Revised on 19/01/2026

Article Published on 01/02/2026

ABSTARCT

Diabetic foot ulcer is one of the major complications of uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus and may ultimately lead to limb amputation if not managed properly. The raising prevalence of Diabetic complications has become a significant burden on society. The number of amputations is rising steadily, highlighting the urgent need for more effective wound management strategies for patients suffering from non-healing diabetic ulcers. Diabetic foot ulcers may occur due to pathological complications, trauma, resulting in chronic wounds. In *Sushruta Chikitsa Sthana*, Acharya Sushruta has described sixty *Upakramas* for the management of *Vrana*, which includes various local and systemic therapeutic measures using different drugs. A 68-year-old female patient with a history of Diabetes Mellitus for past ten years presented with a non-healing foot ulcer of 5 months and was managed as *Dushta Vrana* using *Sthanika Parisheka*, *Kshara karma*, *Avachoomana* and *Jatyadi taila Kavalika*, resulting in satisfactory wound healing. At present, the prevention of limb amputation and effective management of diabetic foot ulcers is major healthcare challenges. A treatment approach is essential to achieve better outcomes in diabetic wound healing.

KEYWORDS: Diabetic foot ulcer, *Dushta vrana*, *Sthanika Parisheka*, *Kshara karma*, *Yashada Bhasma Avachoomana* and *Jatyadi taila Kavalika*.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder with a rapidly increasing global prevalence and is associated with multiple long-term complications. Among these, diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) represents one of the most serious and disabling conditions, contributing significantly to morbidity, mortality.^[1] DFUs primarily arise due to peripheral neuropathy and peripheral arterial disease, which impair protective sensation and blood supply to the lower limbs, thereby predisposing patients to ulcer formation and delayed wound healing.^[2]

Minor foot injuries such as callosities, blisters, cuts, burns, and ingrown toenails often go unnoticed in individuals with diabetes because of sensory neuropathy.^[3] These injuries may progressively enlarge and become infected, eventually leading to chronic non-

healing ulcers. It has been reported that nearly 90% of DFUs are associated with neuropathy, ischemia^[4], or both further-more foot deformities and altered gait patterns increase plantar pressure, resulting in callus formation that further elevates the risk of ulceration.^[5]

The management of DFUs is complex and requires a multidisciplinary approach. Optimal glycaemic control, infection management with appropriate antibiotics, wound debridement, and suitable dressings.^[6] Advanced therapeutic modalities such as negative pressure wound therapy, hyperbaric oxygen therapy, bioengineered skin substitutes, and growth factors have shown promising results in enhancing wound healing.^[7] Despite these advancements, DFUs remain a major cause of lower-limb amputation, emphasizing the need for effective, accessible, and cost-efficient treatment strategies.

In Ayurveda, diabetic foot ulcers can be correlated with *Madhumehajanya Dushta Vrana*. Acharya *Sushruta*, described *Shashti Upakrama* - sixty therapeutic measures for the management of various types of *Vrana*, incorporating both local and systemic interventions.^[8] These principles emphasize wound cleansing, healing promotion, and tissue regeneration. The present case study aims to explore the role of Ayurvedic management in the treatment of a diabetic foot ulcer, highlighting its potentiality as a cost-effective outpatient-based therapeutic approach.^[9]

CASE REPORT

Chief complaints: Patient complaints of non-healing wound over the plantar aspect of metatarsal head of her left foot in the past 5 months, associated with foul-smelling, pus discharge since 1 month.

Patient information: A 68-year-old, female approached our Shalya tantra OPD with a non-healing ulcer below the first metatarsal head of plantar aspect of the left foot for past 5 months. She gave a history of an unnoticed minor injury to the left foot 5 months prior to presentation, following which a small ulcer developed. She presented with mild pain at the wound site, which gradually increased in size. Additionally, she had been experiencing burning sensation and numbness in both lower limbs for the past two years. There was no history suggestive of deep tissue involvement, such as severe pain, exposure of tendon or bone. And also, patient reported swelling of the left foot for one month, for which she consulted in allopathic hospital and was advised with antibiotic, opioids and alternate day dressing with normal saline. The ulcer had remained non-healing despite prior treatment with antibiotics and regular dressings and didn't find any relief so she approached our hospital for further management.

Past History

K/C/O DM Type II in the past 9 years.

Personal History

Appetite –moderate

Bowel –constipated

Micturition –6times /day, 1-2times/night

Sleep –disturbed.

General Examination

Blood pressure -120/70 mmHg

Pulse rate -72bpm

Respiratory rate - 17cpm

Pallor-mild

Icterus, Cyanosis, Clubbing, Lymphadenopathy and Oedema were absent.

Systemic Examination

CNS - Conscious and well oriented to time, place and person.

CVS - S1, S2 heard, no cardiac murmur heard.

RS- Normal vesicular breath sound present, no added sound heard.

P/A-Soft, Non-tender, elastic, no organomegaly present.

Local examination

Site – below first metatarsal head in planter aspect of left foot

Number-one

Size – 2cm x2 cm x5mm

Shape - spherical

Discharge – present

Odour – foul smelling, present

Floor -slough is present

Margin - well defined

Edge -punched out

Base - Muscle

Sinus tract -present

Surrounding skin – callus with blackish discoloration

Tenderness - present

Pulsation - dorsalis pedis and posterior tibial artery anterior tibial artery were palpable.

Sensory Examination

Touch and pain sensations were diminished over the affected foot.

Superficial sensations including light touch, temperature, and pressure were reduced.

Deep sensations and motor function were preserved.

Plantar reflexes – Areflexia

Based on clinical assessment, the patient presented with a Wagner Grade II diabetic foot ulcer and diminished protective sensation.

Results of the blood investigations are reported in the table.

Si no	Investigation	Before treatment	After treatment
1	Hb%	9.2g/dl	10g/dl
2	WBC	7000 cells/cu mm	5000 cells/cu mm
3	ESR	45mm/hour	10mm/hour
4	FBS	200mg/dl	106mg/dl
5	PPBS	250mg/dl	165mg/dl
6	Hba1c	11%	6.2%

TREATMENT

The treatment was planned on the basis of Ayurvedic principles for *Dushta Vrana*.

DAYS	THERAPEUTIC PROCEDURE	ORAL MEDICATIONS
1-7 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Arka Kadali Kshara</i> was applied over the callosity at the wound edges and slough for <i>shatamatrakala</i> and washed with <i>nimbu swarasa</i> followed by <i>Lekhana karma</i>. • <i>Vrana Parisheka</i> was performed using <i>Panchavalkala Kashaya</i>. • Subsequently <i>Yashada Bhasma</i>, <i>Avachoorana</i> and <i>Jathyadi Taila Kavalika</i> were applied, daily dressing was performed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Nishamalaki Choorna</i> 1tsp -0-1tsp (B/F) with lukewarm water • <i>Kaishora guggulu</i> 1-0-1 (A/F) • <i>Haritaki choorna</i> ½ tsp at bed time • <i>Dhatri loha</i> 1-0-1(A/F)
8-16 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Vrana Parisheka</i> was performed using <i>Panchavalkala Kashaya</i> • Subsequently <i>Yashada Bhasma</i>, <i>Avachoorana</i> and <i>Jathyadi Taila Kavalika</i> were applied, daily dressing was performed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Mahamanjistadi Kwatha</i> 20ml-0-20ml (B/F) with lukewarm water • <i>Nishamalaki Choorna</i> 1tsp -0-1tsp (B/F) with lukewarm water • <i>Kaishora guggulu</i> 1-0-1 (A/F) • <i>Haritaki choorna</i> ½ tsp at bed time • <i>Dhatri loha</i> 1-0-1(A/F)
17-40 days	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Vrana Parisheka</i> was performed using <i>Panchavalkala Kashaya</i> • Subsequently <i>Yashada Bhasma</i>, <i>Avachoorana</i> and <i>Jathyadi Taila Kavalika</i> were applied, alternate day dressing was performed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Mahamanjistadi Kwatha</i> 20ml-0-20ml (B/F) with lukewarm water • <i>Nishamalaki Choorna</i> 1tsp -0-1tsp (B/F) with lukewarm water • <i>Kaishora guggulu</i> 1-0-1 (A/F) • <i>Haritaki choorna</i> ½ tsp at bed time • <i>Dhatri loha</i> 1-0-1(A/F)

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

	BEFORE TREATMENT	AFTER TREATMENT
WOUND SIZE	2cm x 2cm x 5mm	ABSENT
SINUS TRACT	PRESENT -1.5cm	ABSENT
DISCHARGE	PRESENT	ABSENT
ODOUR	PRESENT	ABSENT
SLOUGH	PRESENT	ABSENT
TENDERNESS	PRESENT	ABSENT

Before treatment

Day 7

Day 14

Day 21

Day 25

Day 29

Follow-up

No recurrence of the foot ulcer was observed during the 6-month to 1-year follow-up period.

DISCUSSION

The DFUs associated with neuropathy and ischemia need specialized care and appropriate treatment. The primary goal was to achieve complete wound healing along with maintaining the blood sugar level. The second aim was to prevent the further degradation of wound conditions as Diabetics are highly vulnerable to infections.

During the complete course of treatment, the patient was advised *Pathya - Apathya* to enhance wound healing and prevent further complications. The patient was also told to wear diabetic micro cellular rubber (MCR) footwear.

Arka kadali kshara - “क्षरणात् क्षणनाद् क्षारः” — *Kshara* is described as an *Anushastra*, Acharya Dalhana defines *Ksharana* as a property that removes deformed or necrotic tissue due to the alkaline corrosive action, facilitating wound cleansing and debridement. *Arka* (*Calotropis procera*) has *Katu, Tikta Rasa, Laghu, Ruksha, Tikṣṇa Guṇa, Ushṇa Virya, Katu Vipaka, Kapha-Vatahara, vedhanastapana, Kadali (Musa paradisiaca)-Kaṣāya Rasa, Guru, Picchila guna, sheeta Virya, Madhura Vipaka, Ropana, Stambhana Karma. Arka Kadali kshara* which has above said properties, that aid in the removal of devitalized tissue and prepare the wound bed for healing by granulation tissue formation, enhances epithelialization, control discharge and oozing, reduces burning sensation and inflammation.

Yashadha Bhasma- *Bhasmas* are Ayurvedic metallic or mineral preparations reduced to ultra-fine nano- or submicron-sized particles through classical purification (*Shodhana*) and incineration (*Marana*) processes, enhancing their bioavailability and efficacy. Among these, *Yashadha Bhasma*, possessing *Kashaya-Tikta rasa, Sheeta guna* acts as a *Shleshmakala sankochaka, Dahashamaka* (relieving burning), *Kandughna* (reducing itching), *Kusthaghna* (anti-ulcer), and *Pitta-kaphahara* – helps to alleviate burning sensation and pus discharge, while its *Ropana* property promotes granulation tissue formation and accelerates wound healing. Furthermore, its topical application is convenient and easy, making *Yashadha Bhasma* an effective agent for enhancing wound repair and granulation tissue development.

Jatyadi Taila- It possesses *Tikta* and *Kashaya rasa* and *Pitta-Kapha* pacifying properties, is widely used for its wound cleansing (*Vrana Shodhana*), healing (*Ropana*), discharge control (*Pootihara*), and analgesic (*Vedanasthapana*) effects. Its efficacy arises from the synergistic action of its herbal components: *Jati* (Jasmine) provides antibacterial, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory effects due to salicylic acid. *Nimba* (Neem) contains margosin, offering antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic benefits. *Yashtimadhu* (Licorice) promotes tissue regeneration and wound

repair, while Turmeric contributes anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antibacterial activity. *Tutta* (*Woodfordia* fruit extract) facilitates debridement (*Lekhana Karma*), thus helps in enhancing tissue repair and healing.

Panchavalka Kashaya - Combination of five astringent drugs, which shows properties such as *Vrana Shodhana* and *Vrana Ropana*, acts as antiseptic, anti-inflammatory, immune-modulatory, antioxidant, antibacterial and antimicrobial. It is a well-known drug for decreasing microbial load and preventing further infection through its antimicrobial activity.

Shamanoushadi - Aimed at effective glycemic control, improving peripheral blood circulation, and wound healing.

CONCLUSION

The management of Diabetic Foot Ulcers was carried out using classical Ayurvedic formulations to promote wound healing. *Panchavalka Kashaya* provided antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound-purifying effects, supporting *Vrana Shodhana* (cleansing) and *Ropana* (healing). *Jatyadi Taila*, with *Tikta-Kashaya rasa* and *Pitta-Kaphahara* properties, contributed additional wound cleansing, analgesic, and tissue-regenerative effects. *Yashadha Bhasma*, a fine zinc has *Sheeta guna* and *Kashaya-Tikta rasa*, regulated excessive wound secretions, reduced burning and pus discharge, and promoted granulation tissue formation. *Arka Kadali Kshara* facilitated chemical debridement of slough and callosity, preparing the wound bed and providing antimicrobial and scraping action. The combined topical application of these therapies created an optimal environment for effective infection control, enhanced tissue repair, and robust granulation, resulting in accelerated wound healing. This approach demonstrates significant potential as a safe and effective strategy for improving clinical outcomes in wound management.

REFERENCES

1. Boulton AJM, Armstrong DG, Albert SF, et al. Comprehensive foot examination and risk assessment. *Diabetes Care*, 2008; 31(8): 1679–1685.
2. Reiber GE, Lipsky BA, Gibbons GW. The burden of diabetic foot ulcers. *Am J Surg*, 1998; 176(2A): 5S–10S. 1
3. Singh N, Armstrong DG, Lipsky BA. Preventing foot ulcers in patients with diabetes. *JAMA*, 2005; 293(2): 217–228.
4. Edmonds M, Foster A. Diabetic foot ulcers. *BMJ*, 2006; 332(7538): 407–410.
5. Boulton AJM. The diabetic foot. *Med Clin North Am*, 1988; 72(6): 1513–1530.
6. Frykberg RG, Zgonis T, Armstrong DG, et al. Diabetic foot disorders. *J Foot Ankle Surg*, 2006; 45(5 Suppl): S1–S66.

5. Armstrong DG, Boulton AJM, Bus SA. Diabetic foot ulcers and their recurrence. *N Engl J Med*, 2017; 376(24): 2367–2375. 5
6. Lipsky BA, Berendt AR, Cornia PB, et al. IDSA clinical practice guideline for diabetic foot infections. *Clin Infect Dis*, 2012; 54(12): e132–e173. Lavery LA, Armstrong DG, Wunderlich RP, et al. Diabetic foot syndrome. *Diabetes Care*, 2003; 26(5): 1435–1438.
7. Frykberg RG, Banks J. Challenges in the treatment of chronic wounds. *Adv Wound Care*, 2015; 4(9): 560–582.
8. Suśruta. *Suśruta Saṃhitā*, Sutrasthāna – Vraṇa Praśna Adhyāya. Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan. Suśruta. *Suśruta Saṃhitā*, Chikitsāsthāna – Dvivraṇīya Chikitsā Adhyāya. Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Surbharati Prakashan.
9. Mishra A, Sharma R. Ayurvedic management of Madhumehajanya Duṣṭa Vraṇa. *Int J Ayurveda Res*, 2013; 4(2): 89–94.